

2024

A PICTURE OF THE NATION

ISRAEL'S SOCIETY AND ECONOMY IN FIGURES

Avi Weiss

TAUB CENTER

FOR SOCIAL POLICY STUDIES IN ISRAEL

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Israel's Society and Economy in Figures

2024

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Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel

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The basis for many of the figures and analyses in this booklet can be found in the *State of the Nation Report 2023* and other Taub Center publications

Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel

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Foreword

For the past nine years I have dedicated countless hours preparing our annual publication, *A Picture of the Nation*, to make it encompassing and revealing, lucid and enlightening, and geared towards disseminating information while raising interest in the wide variety of topics the Taub Center studies throughout the year.

This year was harder. Israel is at war, a war forced upon it by an evil terror group, Hamas, which attacked Israel on October 7, 2023 (on the holiday of Simchat Torah), brutally killed, raped, and tortured 1,266 Israelis in their homes, including 364 victims at the Nova dance festival and 352 soldiers, and kidnapped 256 Israelis. Since then an additional 293 soldiers have died in battle. As of the time of publication, 125 of the kidnapped are still being held in Gaza, with an unknown number no longer among the living, and the war continues alongside increasingly serious skirmishes on the northern border.

And yet, despite everything, with a heavy heart and never-ending thoughts about the hostages, the victims, our brave soldiers, and their families, our work must continue. As in past years, we present the situation and trends in each of the areas researched by the Center — macroeconomics, labor markets, welfare, health, education, early childhood, the environment and health, and demography. In addition, we present two Spotlights with some interesting and important findings from new studies published over the last year. The first looks at aging and the long-term care insurance market in Israel, and demonstrates some of the difficulties Israel will be facing in the coming years and decades and some of the implications. The second shows how

class sizes have changed in Israel since the turn of the century, with some findings that were central to the recent decision by the Shapiro committee to address this and other issues in the education system.

I especially want to point to the section on Environment and Health. This is a new Research and Policy Initiative at the Taub Center, formed in cooperation with the Forum for Health and the Environment. The section is based on the first completed pieces of research by members of that team. I am proud of the fact that the Taub Center has engaged on this important research frontier.

Throughout the publication you will find repeated reference to the war and its effects on Israel and its population. Those references cannot, and should not, be avoided, and must continue to inform everything we do. Our thoughts are with all those who have faced such incredible hardship since October 7, our hearts go out to them all, and especially to our kidnapped compatriots, in all their diversity: Jews, Arabs, labor migrants, secular, religious, right, left, peaceniks, supporters of Greater Israel. We pray that this war will soon end with all the hostages returned to their homes and able to begin healing.

I trust that the findings presented in this book will help inform decision makers and the general public, and continue to serve as an asset to all its readers.

Prof. Avi Weiss

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Professor of Economics, Bar-Ilan University

Macro-Economic Trends

The war that ensued in response to the Hamas attack on October 7th has harmed the Israeli economy. The damage in the fourth quarter of 2023 was immediate and unavoidable, resulting from large parts of the economy being temporarily shut down, a decrease in employment as hundreds of thousands were called up to the army reserves, the closure of schools and its effect on working parents, the evacuation of hundreds of thousands from their homes in the South and the North, and more. With that, the Israeli economy continues to demonstrate resilience, as it has in previous wars and military operations.

In this section, we will first examine the state of the Israeli economy coming into this war and then describe some of the macroeconomic effects of the war.

After COVID and until the war, GDP returned to its expected level

In the graph: The graph compares per capita GDP and private consumption since the COVID crisis to their expected values given long-term growth rates. The pandemic hit the economy hard in the second quarter of 2020, but, since then, it has rebounded, and, by the third quarter of 2021, it passed the expected levels had there been no crisis. As a result of the war, the final quarter of 2023 contracted by 5.8% relative to that quarter in 2022, returning to its third quarter 2021 level. The first quarter of 2024 saw the start of a recovery with per capita GDP shrinking by *only* 3.1% relative to the same quarter in the previous year. Per capita private consumption has not returned to its expected level. In the last quarter of 2023, private consumption per capita fell by 9.7% relative to the parallel quarter in 2022, with the first quarter 2024 gap falling to 3.6%.

Beyond the graph: The contraction of private consumption was partially a result of the COVID period restrictions. Even before the war, 2023 saw a slowdown in the growth of private consumption, apparently due to the rapid rise in interest rates. The share of private consumption in GDP dropped from 53% in 2019 to 49% at the end of 2023.

**GDP per capita and private consumption per capita
NIS, 2015 prices**

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Following the war — a rapid rise in public consumption and a decline in the other components of GDP

In the graph: The graph shows the large changes in the components of GDP in the final quarter of 2023 and the first quarter of 2024 versus the same quarter in the year before.

Beyond the graph: The large decline in investment in the last quarter of 2023 was almost completely offset by the rise in public consumption (the weight of each of these indices in GDP is about 20%). Moreover, net exports grew in the fourth quarter of 2023 relative to the same quarter in 2022, as the rate of decrease in imports was greater than that in exports — components with similar weights in GDP (each is about 30%). Since an increase in net exports contributes to a rise in GDP, its decline can be attributed to a decrease in private consumption. These trends weakened significantly in the first quarter of 2024. Investments, and to an even greater degree private consumption, fell by less, and a small deficit emerged in the current account, leading to a smaller hit to GDP growth.

The influence of the war on GDP components
Quarter to quarter comparison

Source: Benjamin Bental, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Until the outbreak of war — government expenditure by the two latest governments were similar

Background: The graph presents government expenditure on civilian ministries and for the defense establishment. Data for civilian ministries are adjusted to changes in the CPI as well as to the size of the population, since they are determined by individual demands like health and education services, which are dependent on the population size. Defense expenditure is a collective demand that is not directly connected to population size, and so the adjustment is relative to the CPI alone.

In the graph: There is a great similarity between the expenditures of the *government of change*, which was in office in 2022, and the current government for the first three quarters of 2022 and 2023. In December 2022, there was a sharp increase in civilian ministry expenditures, a phenomenon that has been seen in previous years and seems to result from the desire of ministries to use up their budgets

by year end. With the outbreak of the war, adjusted civilian expenditure grew in October by NIS 5 billion relative to the comparable period in the previous year, and in November, it rose an additional 2 billion shekel relative to the comparable period. Surprisingly, December's data adjusted by the CPI and for population size are similar in both years. Nevertheless, since the beginning of 2024, there are signs of an increase in adjusted civilian ministry expenditures relative to the two previous years.

Defense expenditure did not experience changes until the outbreak of the war. In the final quarter of 2023, defense expenditure grew by NIS 17 billion relative to the comparable period in 2022. In the first four months of 2024, expenditure increased by almost 150% relative to the same months in 2023 — NIS 53 billion versus NIS 23 billion.

Beyond the graph: The defense budget that was approved for 2024 is about NIS 114.5 billion, relative to NIS 64.4 billion approved before the war. Based on the demands of the defense ministries, security expenditures for the coming years are expected to be higher by about NIS 20 billion a year relative to the pre-war years. The Bank of Israel believes that an increase of more than NIS 10 billion a year in this budget line would jeopardize the fiscal stability of the country.

Defense and non-defense government expenditures NIS billion

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Finance, Accountant General Division

The increase in the deficit will lead to a sharp rise in the debt-to-GDP ratio

In the graph: The graph allows a tracking of the fiscal conduct of the government over the two crises since the start of the current decade.

Beyond the graph: In response to the COVID crisis, the government put in place emergency measures both in the health and economy spheres. Consequently, the deficit reached the unprecedented level of 11.3% of GDP in 2020, and in 2021, it remained high. These deficits caused the public debt-to-GDP ratio to jump from 60% in 2019 to 70.7% in 2020 and to 68% in 2021. The rapid growth in the economy in 2022 and the fiscal conduct of the government created a government budget surplus of 0.6% of GDP in 2022 and returned the debt-to-GDP ratio to near its pre-crisis level, 60.8%. The projected deficit for 2023 prior to the war, 1.3% of GDP, was fiscally responsible, and the debt-to-GDP ratio was expected to be 60.5% of GDP. In 2024, the deficit was

expected to be 1.5% of GDP with a debt-to-GDP ratio falling to 59% of GDP.

The war changed all of those predictions completely and 2023 ended with a deficit of 4.2% of GDP and a debt ratio of 62.1% of GDP. Predictions at the time of the new budget passage for 2024 was that the deficit would grow to 6.6% of GDP, with the debt ratio growing to 66% of GDP. It is already clear that the deficit will exceed this forecast substantially, and will conservatively be 8%. This forecast is based on the assumption that war does not break out in the North, and that the fiscal policies awaiting approval by the Finance Committee will be carried out.

Implications: The rise in the debt-to-GDP ratio may further endanger Israel's credit rating and lead to an additional rise in interest payments.

Budget surplus as a percentage of GDP since the beginning of the decade and 2024 forecasts

Source: Benjamin Bental, Taub Center | Data: Bank of Israel

The worker productivity gap between Israel and the OECD has narrowed, but not disappeared

Background: In 2010, Israeli workers worked an average of 1,954 hours a year, 13% more than in the median OECD countries. In 2022, the average number of work hours in Israel was somewhat lower, 1,892 hours, while the gap with the OECD grew to 16%.

In the graph: In 2010, productivity per work hour in Israel was 23% lower than in the median OECD country (Spain). This gap narrowed in 2022 to 10% (Spain).

Beyond the graph: The narrowing of the gap is in part due to a decline in productivity towards the end of the pandemic in the OECD, but not in Israel. The narrowing of the gap was furthered by a rise in the growth rate of productivity in Israel that began in the middle of the previous decade. From the middle of the last decade, productivity per work hour grew in high tech and in information and communications by 45%. Traditional industries also saw an improvement of 30% (primarily following a drop of about 20% in work hours). The rise in the portion of high tech in GDP to about 18% in 2022 also contributed to an improvement in productivity per work hour as seen in the graph.

GDP per work hour
PPP dollars, 2017 prices

Source: Benjamin Bentall and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: OECD

The rise and fall in high-tech investment matched international variability, but was more extreme

In the graph: Investment in high-tech industries in Israel reached a peak of \$8.2 billion in the last quarter of 2021. The COVID crisis, which was characterized by near zero interest rates and the absence of investment opportunities in other industries, was a period of top investments worldwide in high tech. In 2023, investments in Israeli high tech returned to their pre-crisis levels. A similar trend was seen globally, although it was somewhat less extreme.

Beyond the graph: In an international comparison, investment in Israel is exceptional. At its peak, high-tech investments in Israel were 8% of those in the US, versus 4% between 2015 and 2018 (GDP in Israel is about 1.6% of the GDP in the US). Internationally, high-tech investment in Israel was about 3.5% of the worldwide investment at its peak, versus 1.5% between 2015 and 2018 (GDP in Israel is about 0.3% of the worldwide GDP). In 2023 and in the first quarter of 2024, the share of investment in Israel versus investment in the US and throughout the world returned to pre-pandemic levels.

High-tech investment in Israel

Billion dollars

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: IVC

The planned judicial reform and the war led to a weakening of the shekel

In the graph: The graph tracks the relationship between the shekel-dollar exchange rate and the US dollar relative to the S&P 500 index on a daily basis. The relationship between the two variables seems tight and consistent, with structural changes resulting from dramatic events in the Israeli economy.

The graph distinguishes between different periods. The first covers approximately two and half years, until the outbreak of the COVID pandemic. Following the intervention of the Bank of Israel in the foreign currency market, which was intended to weaken the shekel, and an adjustment period in the first quarter of 2020, the relationship between the two variables was renewed until the end of 2022, but at an exchange rate that was about NIS 0.35 higher than in the previous period (controlling for the S&P 500 index). With the announcement of the plans for a judicial reform at the beginning of January 2023, the connection was again broken and the exchange rate went up relative to the level that would have been expected

on the basis of the previous period. Based on this calculation, the devaluation of the shekel on the eve of the war was 17% (about NIS 0.55). Since the war, the negative relationship between the two variables has been restored, but with significant deviations from the trend line because of the war. The excess devaluation of the shekel is rising, and is currently about 25% (about 75 agorot) of the rate that would have been expected before the announcement of the judicial reform, given the level of the S&P 500. It thus seems that the changes in the exchange rate and its relationship with the S&P 500 reflect the internal political tension and the dangers of war.

Beyond the graph: The very existence of a negative correlation between these two variables is apparently due to the intention of institutional investors to balance between shekel and dollar components in their investment portfolios. When the S&P 500 index rises, investors sell part of the dollar assets in exchange for shekels, thus strengthening the shekel.

Shekel to dollar exchange rate and the S&P 500 index

Note: The relationship presented in the graph was first proposed by Atar, Spiegel, and Spitzer (2023).

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: Bank of Israel; S&P

Israel — the most expensive of the OECD countries

Background: To compare prices across countries, the cost of a basket of private consumer goods in the country currency is calculated and is then translated into a single currency (usually the US dollar) using the exchange rate on the foreign currency market. According to the economic theory, price levels in wealthy countries are expected to be higher than in less wealthy ones, primarily due to the non-tradable components (like rent) in the consumer basket.

In the graph: Using this calculation, Israel in 2022 was the most expensive country in the OECD, and the price levels were 38% higher than the OECD average. The graph indicates the existence of a parabolic relationship between per capita GDP and the level of prices in the OECD countries in 2022.

Beyond the graph: Israel's exceptionalism stands out and may be related to the relative weight of housing in the private consumer basket. For instance, Finland is similar to Israel in size and GDP per capita and close to the regression curve, but the weight of housing in Finland's basket is considerably lower.

Price levels relative to GDP per capita, Israel and the OECD countries, 2022

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Labor Markets

In this section, we focus first on developments in Israel's labor force from the onset of COVID-19 until the October war, and then on how the war affected the labor market. We show not only the hit that the market took, but also the partial recovery, demonstrating the resilience of the Israeli market, seen both after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and this year as the war proceeded.

An increase in employment for Arabs and Haredim, men and women

In the graph: There has been a fairly consistent increase in employment among Arab and Haredi men over the past two years. Among women, employment rates reached their highest levels ever for the second year in a row. Overall, while the rate of employment among men by the summer of 2022 returned to that in the summer of 2019 (82%), among women there was an increase of about 2 percentage points (77% vs 75%). The rates have increased only a little since then.

Beyond the graph: The data for Haredi men should be treated with caution. Employment among men defined as Haredi according to the National Economic Council was much lower than the figure presented in the graph. Most of the increase originated among men who self-identify as Haredi but do not meet the NEC definition, and this group's rapid expansion explains about 44% of the increase between the first half of 2019 and the same period in 2023. The rest is concentrated in the 55–64 age group, a population not expected to remain in the labor market in the long term.

Employment rate among ages 25–64, by sector and gender

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil S. Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Israel's recovery from COVID-19 outpaced that in other OECD countries

Background: Israel's recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic was truly remarkable, highlighting the economy's resilience and lending hope for a speedy recovery from the current war. Wage increases in Israel following the pandemic, and, in particular, over the past year, are noteworthy relative to wage changes in other high-income countries.

In the graph: The real wage in Israel rose both between 2019 and 2022 and during the year leading up to the war. In contrast, the graph shows that wages were eroded in most high-income countries during the pandemic and following it, and in particular over the past year. Thus, the real average wage in OECD countries fell on average by 2% between 2019 and 2022 and by 4% between 2022 and 2023. In contrast, Israel is the only country in the OECD in which the average real wage rose during both periods.

Rate of change in real hourly wage in the OECD countries, 2019/2022 and 2022/2023

Note: Data for Israel are for employees only.

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil S. Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Unemployment due to economic reasons has neared its pre-war level

Background: The Labor Force Survey of the Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) distinguishes between those who are not working and who continue to actively seek employment (unemployed) and those who were employed during the survey period but absent from their place of work for economic reasons. These reasons are usually downsizing at the work place or a temporary absence from work (up to 30 days). The survey also identifies workers who have stopped working due to lay-offs or work place closure over the past two years.

In the graph: On the eve of the war, the unemployment rate was very low — 3.4%. This rate is calculated out of the labor force, which was about 64% of the population in Israel aged 15 and over. The rate of those temporarily absent from work

and the rate of those who had stopped working altogether were also quite low. With the outbreak of the war, the share of those unemployed remained stable, but the share of those temporarily absent from work for economic reasons rose to 6.3%. Nevertheless, this rate has declined rapidly, and, in April 2024, it was only slightly higher than in non-crisis times.

Beyond the graph: The half a percentage point rise (40,000 people) that began in November 2023 in the rate of those who were either laid off or lost their place of employment due to work place closures in the past two years is noteworthy. This rise contributed to a simultaneous decline of 1.5 percentage points in the share of those participating in the labor force.

Unemployment rate and non-participation in the labor market

Source: Benjamin Bental, Taub Center | Data: CBS

A decline in the share of those absent from work for economic reasons

Background: At the end of 2023, about 2.3 million men and a bit less than 2.2 million women were employed in Israel.

In the graph: Slightly less than one-quarter of workers were absent from their place of work for at least a week in October 2023. Among men, army reserve duty was one of the most prevalent reasons for this absence. The other main reasons for absence were economic reasons — i.e., work closures — and other reasons, which were most likely caused by school closures in October and the need to care for children at home. With the reopening of schools, this reason disappeared almost completely in the months that followed. Absence from work due to economic reasons also declined, and, as seen in the previous graph, these rates have nearly returned to normal. The large increase in those absent from work in April for reasons of illness or vacation is due to the Passover holiday, which fell in April.

Number of and reasons for absence from work for the entire week

Source: Benjamin Bental, Taub Center | Data: CBS

The fall in employment and the rate of recovery differed greatly across industries

In the figure: The Hamas attack on October 7 and the ensuing war affected industries differently. The hardest hit on a national level were construction and accommodation and food services where employment fell in the first month by over 40%, for different reasons in the two industries. The source of the decline in the former came from the labor side, with Palestinian workers no longer allowed into the country and Israeli Arabs either unwilling to work during the initial turmoil or unwanted by employers, while the latter came more from the demand side with a sharp fall in foreign and local tourism. The different paths to recovery have, therefore, also been quite different, with relatively quick recovery in construction as Israeli workers returned to their work places while the recovery in tourism was slower. Transportation and education also were initially hit hard as schools closed and people stayed home, but both recovered quickly.

Workers temporarily absent from work for the entire week, selected economic sectors

Source: Benjamin Bental, Taub Center | Data: CBS

High and increasing levels of job satisfaction throughout the working population

In the graph: At least since the beginning of this century, Israeli workers have been, in general, satisfied in their places of work. Job satisfaction rose among workers until 2019, with the majority of the increase happening until 2011. In addition, the share of those who are very satisfied with their work out of all those expressing satisfaction (satisfied and very satisfied) increased. This was found across all groups of workers: men and women, self-employed and employees, those working in the private and public sector, as well as those with higher education and those without. In 2020, with the outbreak of the COVID epidemic in Israel, there was an additional rise in job satisfaction.

Beyond the graph: Self-reports of rising job satisfaction during the COVID crisis (2020–2021) may reflect the feelings of some workers that they were happy to maintain their place of work, that they returned to work after a period of unemployment or involuntary furlough, or due to receiving unemployment benefits during the time they were on temporary involuntary furlough.

Job satisfaction among workers ages 25–64, 2002–2022

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Significant changes in study majors for a BA

In the graph: Considerable changes were observed in study majors. The share of students in mathematics, statistics, computer science, engineering, and architecture grew significantly, at a rate of 29% among Jews and Others and 23% among Arabs. In contrast, the share of students in the social sciences, the humanities, education, and art dropped by 15% among Jews and Others and 21% among Arabs.

There were sector-related trends in several study majors. The share of medical and paramedical students within total Arab students dropped by 30% although the number of students increased, while among Jewish and Other students their share grew by 54%. The decrease in most of the healthcare professions (including medicine) among Arabs may be a combination of a rise in the total number of Arab students and an increase in the proportion studying abroad. The weight of students in business and managerial science within the total number of Arab students has doubled during the period, while the weight of students in these professions within the total Jewish and Other student population has not changed.

Number of students in higher education, by study major and sector

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil S. Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Welfare

While the welfare system has always been central to ensuring the well-being of individuals and families in Israel. This became more apparent since the onset of the October war, with social workers and the National Insurance Institute taking center stage in efforts to assist those Israelis harmed by the war. This, despite the severe lack of resources dedicated to welfare services and the substantial shortage of personnel in the field. In the following pages, we first show some of the broad effects the war has had on the welfare system, and then present current data on the system and discuss some of the substantial challenges it faces.

A sharp rise in the number of unemployment benefit recipients as a result of the war

Background: As a result of the war that broke out in October 2023, many individuals lost their place of work or were placed on involuntary leave without pay from work. As during the COVID period, the government took a number of steps to temporarily expand entitlements to unemployment benefits.

In the graph: The number of recipients of unemployment benefits before the war was relatively low, although showing signs of a slow rise. In October 2023, the number of recipients more than doubled, while as of December, the trend has begun to reverse.

Beyond the graph: In contrast to the pandemic period when the government encouraged residents to remain at home, during the war, individuals were encouraged to leave their homes (under the restrictions placed by the Home Front Command) and go to work in order to allow the economy to return to full activity to the extent possible.

Number of unemployment benefit recipients

Source: Nir Kaidar, Taub Center | Data: National Insurance Institute

A dramatic rise in the number of those receiving assistance under the Victims of Hostile Actions Law

Background: From the start of the war, the National Insurance Institute began to locate injured people and the families of the civilian hostages and victims in order to provide immediate financial support to fund other needs. Their actions were undertaken in the framework of the Victims of Hostile Actions Law 1970, which was extended to include the relatives of missing persons and hostages under an agreement with the Ministry of Finance.

In the graph: This led to a dramatic increase in the number of people receiving grants under this law. Since the beginning of the war, 64,898 injured persons were added to the 6,029 persons who had been receiving benefits due to disability, and the number of families of deceased persons rose from 1,890 to 2,983. The permanent status of these individuals and the level of their benefits will be decided at a later date. The National Insurance Institute also provides an accommodation grant to people who evacuated their homes of their own volition and were not admitted to facilities funded by the state, and a return grant for evacuees who have returned home.

Number of recipients of assistance under the Victims of Hostile Actions Law

Note: The number of disabled individuals is updated to April 2, 2024; the number of dependents to March 31, 2024.

Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat (Madhala), Taub Center | Data: National Insurance Institute

A decline in the number of evacuees in hotels, mostly among those from the South

Background: Since October 7th, more than 150,000 residents have been forced to evacuate their homes. In the first months of the war, the majority of them were housed in hotels paid for by the state. Over time, many have left the hotels and relocated to rental housing or have returned to their homes (primarily those in the South).

In the graph: The graph shows the number of evacuees in hotels grouped by residents of the North and the South (the division by area of original residence is available only since the second week of December). The gradual decline in the number of those remaining in hotels can be seen, with the majority of those who have left being from the South.

Beyond the graph: In a survey published in November dealing with evacuees and the significance of long-term evacuation, we showed that displacement for long periods of time have a number of effects: emotional, employment, family relations, and more.

Evacuees in hotels by region of residence

Source: Nir Kaidar, Taub Center | Data: Yachad data system

Difficulties filling social worker positions in social service departments

Background: In the years prior to October 7, 2023, the welfare service system in Israel suffered from under-funding, a shortage of manpower, and unequal allocation of resources among localities.

In the graph: In June 2023, 747 social work positions were unfilled in local authority social service departments. This problem was felt most strongly in weaker authorities. The data show that in authorities with the lowest socioeconomic status (Cluster 1), where the social distress is the greatest, the number of unfilled positions was greater than the national average. Following the sharp rise in demand with the outbreak of the war, the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs has increased the number of social work positions in local social service departments. In May 2024, the number of positions was 6,679, an increase of 407 positions since June 2023. The number of filled positions grew by 259 to 5,784.

Beyond the graph: The difficulty in filling positions is typical of the past decade, and, in particular, the past few years. It is linked to employment conditions, heavy caseloads, pay, and the low status of social workers.

Share of filled social work positions and number of unfilled positions in social service departments

Note: Data are from June of every year from 2015 through 2023. Positions financed by the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs.

Source: Shavit Ben-Porat (Madhala) and John Gal, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs

Changes in social expenditure as a result of COVID and the war

In the graph: Social expenditure, which grew significantly during the pandemic period, again contracted. In 2023, it grew to about NIS 340 billion. This is an increase of NIS 29 billion in real terms (and about NIS 35 billion in current prices). The majority of the increase in the past year has been in social security, in particular following war-related expenditures of the National Insurance Institute.

Beyond the graph: The portion of the budget that is dedicated to social expenditure between 2022 and 2023 was particularly high relative to its level over the course of the past two decades, and even surpassed that during the COVID crisis. In those years, 61% of total government expenditure (without debt repayment or interest) was dedicated to social issues — a rise of 2 percentage points relative to social expenditure in the budget in 2021.

Social expenditure in Israel
NIS billion, 2023 prices

Source: John Gal, Shavit Ben-Porat (Madhala), and Adi Tarabeih, Taub Center |
Data: Ministry of Finance; National Insurance Institute

A rise in social expenditures

Background: Social services, part of the social welfare system, are allocated the smallest portion of social expenditure in the state budget.

In the graph: Between 2022 and 2023, there was a rise in expenditure devoted to these services, with a portion dedicated to an increase in the budget of the Ministry of Immigrant Integration for the integration of immigrants from Ukraine and Russia. Aside from this budget addition, there were additions to activities of the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs and for employment programs, while the spending on housing, which had been substantially reduced over the years, grew. A look at social ministry budgets as a percent of total government expenditure shows that the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs and the Ministry of Housing received less than 2%, while the other ministries receive less than 1% each.

Expenditure on social welfare areas as a percent of total government expenditure

Source: John Gal, Shavit Ben-Porat (Madhala), and Adi Tarabeih, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Finance

The Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs budget stabilized after COVID, and then the war broke out

In the graph: Over the past decade, the budget of the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs has more than doubled, although in the years since the pandemic, it appears that there is more stability. Between 2020 and 2022, the budget was about NIS 10 billion. Budget data for 2023 shows an increase in this budget to NIS 10.8 billion, and, according to the approved budget for 2024, it appears that there will be an additional increase.

Beyond the graph: The expected increase in the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs budget is spread over the areas under the ministry's purview. Total social expenditure, which grew in 2023, is expected to remain high and even increase, primarily reflecting an expected rise in social security spending, including a rise in spending by the National Insurance Institute and in payments by the Ministry of Defense for rehabilitation and to families.

Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs budget
NIS billion, 2023 prices

Note: The data are budget execution data, except for 2024 which reflects the approved budget.

Source: Shavit Ben-Porat (Madhala) and John Gal, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Finance

A rise in general disability benefits, but not in income support

Background: In the past few years, there have been increases in the general disability benefit for those without any other source of income as well as for those who are able to integrate into the labor force to a limited extent. The main changes occurred with the change to the General Disability Law in February 2018 following a sustained strike by the organization of persons with disabilities. In contrast, the income support program, which provides a final safety net for those who are unable to join the labor market and have particularly low income, is set quite low with multiple bureaucratic obstacles for those attempting to uptake their rights.

In the graph: In 2015, the level of assistance in the two programs was quite similar, with a difference between them of NIS 836 per month. As a result of the policy change, the average monthly allowance for income support recipients in 2023 was NIS 2,316, and the average disability allowance was NIS 4,214, a difference of NIS 1,898. Since both benefits serve the same purpose — to provide a safety net for individuals and families to live and work with dignity — the justification for such a gap is unclear.

General disability and income support: Average monthly benefit levels over time

NIS, 2023 prices

Source: John Gal, Shavit Ben-Porat (Madhala), and Adi Tarabeih, Taub Center | Data: National Insurance Institute

Substantial differences across local authorities in their social service expenditure

Background: Substantial gaps across local authorities are prevalent in the average expenditure per service user of welfare services

In the graph: Dividing budgeting patterns for welfare services in Israel's local authorities indicates substantial gaps across local authorities in terms of their average expenditure per service user. Authorities in the highest socioeconomic clusters spend more than double on welfare services per service user than those authorities in the lowest cluster. Dividing by population group, the differences come into sharper focus. In the Bedouin local authorities, the average welfare expenditure is only NIS 5,103, versus NIS 13,148 in cities belonging to the Forum-15 grouping of the economically strongest authorities.

Annual average expenditure on welfare services per service user, by population group, 2021

NIS

Note: By main population group in the authority.

Source: John Gal and Adi Tarabeih, Taub Center | Data: CBS; Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs

A high level of food insecurity in Israel

Background: According to the UN Food and Agriculture Organization, food insecurity is the “lack of regular access to enough safe and nutritious food for normal growth and development and an active and healthy life.” Food security is built on four pillars that must be met at the same time: food availability, access for the individual or family, the physical ability to consume the food, and the stability of the three dimensions over time.

In an NII survey from 2021, it was found that 16.2% of families in Israel lived in food insecurity and 8.2% suffered from serious food insecurity. The UN Food and Agriculture Organization publishes an international comparison based on a survey looking at accessibility to sufficient food. The survey looked at the amount and quality of food, as well as the need to limit consumption, skip meals, or go without food for a day.

In the graph: An international comparison between welfare states shows that levels of food insecurity vary between 2% of the population in Switzerland and 14% in Israel and New Zealand. The OECD average is 7.5%.

Food insecurity in welfare states, average for 2018–2022

Source: John Gal, Ori Oberman, and Nir Kaidar, Taub Center | Data: FAO

Spotlight

Long-Term Care

Israel is getting older, much more quickly than in the past. This aging has widespread implications for the labor market, the welfare needs and the health needs of the population, and in particular on long-term care. The percentage of the elderly in need of long-term care is substantially larger than in most other developed countries, and as the population ages, the needs grow exponentially.

There is a sharp increase in the growth rate of the population aged 75+

In the graph: Israel's population is rapidly aging. Between 2010 and 2020, the adult population over age 75 grew by an average of 9,000 individuals annually. The actual annual growth rate from 2020 to 2023 together with the expected rate until 2040 indicates an average growth of 20,000–30,000 individuals aged 75 or over per year.

Beyond the graph: Life expectancy in Israel continues to rise; from 1999 until 2021, life expectancy of a 65-year-old man rose by 3 years (16.4 versus 19.5 years), and for a 65-year-old woman by 3.5 years (18.5 versus 22 years). These increases present a challenge with regard to enabling the elderly more healthy years at high levels of functioning. In order to allow the elderly to age in place, in line with today's welfare policies, there is a need for an overall policy to integrate between the different agencies dealing with this population.

Number of individuals aged 75 and over in the population
Thousands

Source: Nir Kaidar, Nadav Davidovitch, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: CBS

The population receiving long-term care benefits grew rapidly relative to the population of senior citizens

Background: Long-term care benefits are extended to elderly in need of assistance with basic daily function activities. Long-term care services are split between health funds, the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs, the National Insurance Institute (NII), and the Ministry of Health. Currently, more than 340,000 elderly citizens receive these benefits from the NII.

In the graph: The growth rate of recipients of long-term care benefits from the NII and from group insurance is substantially faster than among those receiving old-age benefits. Between 2012 and 2023, the number of those qualifying for NII long-term care benefits grew by 118%, versus a growth rate of 45% in the number of those receiving old-age benefits.

Beyond the graph: This sharp rise in long-term care recipients has a large impact on the actuarial balance of the NII. Based on NII projections, the expected growth is liable to speed up depletion of NII funds. The rise in the number of recipients is also being felt in the private long-term insurance held by the health funds, and led to a rise in premiums and diminishing of benefits for insurance holders over the past year.

Index of the number of long-term care and old-age benefits recipients

2012 = 100

Source: Nir Kaidar, Nadav Davidovitch, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: Capital Market, Insurance and Savings Authority; National Insurance Institute

A large majority of public and private expenditure on nursing care is for home care

In the graph: In 2022, national expenditure on long-term care was about NIS 23.6 billion. Of this, NIS 18.7 billion was spent on community care services, NIS 3.8 billion on long-term care hospitalization, NIS 0.7 billion on assisted living facilities, and NIS 0.4 billion on complex nursing care facilities. Of this, the portion of public expenditure was NIS 16.7 billion (about 71%). Private expenditure was NIS 7 billion, of which NIS 4.4 billion was for home care.

Public and private expenditure on long-term care by expenditure areas, 2022

Estimate, NIS million

Source: Nir Kaidar, Nadav Davidovitch, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Finance; Ministry of Health; Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs; National Insurance Institute

Israel is a leader in the portion of elderly requiring long-term care

In the graph: An international comparison shows that Israel ranks high among OECD countries in the share of individuals over age 65 receiving long-term care benefits. Israel's high ranking stems from the large share of long-term care recipients in the community. Israel ranks low in terms of the share of those in long-term care facilities.

Beyond the graph: It is important to note that OECD data are for 2021. Since then, there was a substantial rise in the number receiving benefits in Israel.

Proportion of senior citizens receiving long-term care in Israel and in selected OECD countries, 2021

Source: Nir Kaidar, Nadav Davidovitch, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: OECD

The likelihood of requiring long-term care grows significantly from age 70

In the graph: The cumulative likelihood of needing long-term care rises substantially with advanced age. The probability that someone will be in need of such care at age 80 is 23% for men and 26% for women (that is, 1 in 4 individuals will be in need of long-term care at age 80). For those in their 90s, the likelihood is 48% and 57% for men and women, respectively. At younger ages, the likelihood of needing such care is low.

Beyond the graph: It is important to note that these calculations are based on existing data from 2020, and do not take into account the rise in benefits since 2020 or additional changes that may take place in the future in terms of claims and life expectancy for those in need of long-term care.

Cumulative probability of needing long-term care, by age and gender, 2020

Source: Nir Kaidar, Nadav Davidovitch, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: Capital Market, Insurance and Savings Authority

Health

Israel's health system is well known for its structure and its successful performance in areas that include longevity, low infant mortality, and healthy life years (HALYs). Despite all this, quantitative data point to substantial deficiencies in many areas, as well as demographic, socioeconomic, and geographic inequalities, which seem to indicate that, left unaddressed, the strong performances of the past could erode. This became all too clear during the COVID-19 pandemic and even more so during the current war, with Israel's health system coming close to its breaking point. In the coming pages, we show some of the deficiencies that need to be addressed, especially given the expected substantial increase in Israel's elderly population over the next decade.

Per-capita expenditure on health is in the bottom third of the OECD

In the graph: Per-capita health expenditure in Israel in PPP (purchasing power parity) terms was \$3,596 in 2022, which is lower than in most of the OECD countries.

Beyond the graph: The comparison to other countries does not account for factors that are likely to affect this expenditure, such as the structure of the health system, the

country’s employment structure, and the population’s age profile. Adjusting for age — which is necessary given Israel’s relatively young population — somewhat reduces the disparity between Israel and most of the OECD countries, but still leaves it in the bottom third.

National per-capita health expenditure and as a percentage of GDP, age-adjusted, international comparison, 2022

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Natan Lev, and Baruch Levi, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Government's share of health expenditure is among the lowest in the OECD

Background: In 2022, the national expenditure on healthcare in nominal prices was NIS 132.6 billion, which was 7.3% of GDP, much lower than the average in OECD countries (9.3%). This places Israel in the lower third of the OECD countries.

In the graph: Israel ranks even lower in the public share of healthcare expenditures, with only Portugal, South Korea, and Chile ranked lower.

Beyond the graph: While the percentage of national expenditure out of GDP has remained stable since the passage of the National Health Insurance Law, the average in the OECD has risen, resulting in the current disparity. This gap is reflected in the growing needs of the healthcare system, from the updating of the healthcare basket to investment in the healthcare work force and infrastructure. After a rise in expenditure during the pandemic, its portion from GDP returned to the *old normal*, characterized by low public expenditure. Given the current war and the great needs in areas such as mental health and rehabilitation, the underfunding of the health system represents a significant challenge.

Public expenditure on health as a percent of national expenditure on health, international comparison, 2022

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Natan Lev, and Baruch Levi, Taub Center | Data: OECD

The number of physicians per capita is slightly lower than the OECD average

Background: Healthcare work force planning is of critical importance to the future of the healthcare system. This affects the healthcare system's long-term ability to meet the needs of the population over time. To this end, precise projections are required that account for demographic, economic, social, and other variables.

In the graph: Over the past decade the number of physicians per capita in Israel has risen somewhat, from 3 physicians per 1,000 population to 3.3, and is approaching the level in 2000. Yet it remains lower than the OECD average.

Beyond the graph: In recent years, the Ministry of Health has invested a great deal of effort in work force planning as well as in finding solutions to persistent problems, such as low numbers of care providers per capita; the sub-optimal distribution of the work force leading to scarcities in some of the professions and specializations; the unequal geographic distribution of care providers; and the migration of high-quality work force to the private health sector.

Number of physicians per 1,000 population, international comparison

Note: Data are for the most current year available.

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Natan Lev, and Baruch Levi, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Israel has the highest percentage of physicians trained outside of the country among the OECD countries

In the graph: Another important factor to consider is the healthcare system's reliance on graduates of foreign medical schools. Their proportion out of the total number of physicians in Israel is close to 60%, which is by far the highest among the OECD countries. Furthermore, their geographic distribution is unequal; their share in the periphery is about 80%.

Beyond the graph: The Yatziv reform from 2019, which reduced the list of foreign medical schools recognized in Israel will result in a substantial fall in the number of new physicians entering the system in 2025, especially in the periphery. At the same time, the total number of new medical licenses is on an upward trend: in 2021, 2,024 new licenses were issued, 2.8 times more than those issued in 2010. Of those, 776 were issued to graduates of medical schools in Israel, 2.2 times more than in 2010. However, these numbers are not sufficient in view of the increase in, and aging of, Israel's population, and, therefore, further solutions are required, as discussed on the next page.

The share of physicians trained abroad out of all physicians, international comparison

Note: Data are for the most current year available.

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Natan Lev, and Baruch Levi, Taub Center | Data: OECD

The number of medical school graduates relative to the population is the lowest in the OECD

In the graph: While there has been a significant increase in the number of medical students in Israel during the past two decades, this number per capita was still the lowest among the OECD countries in 2020–2022.

Beyond the graph: To improve the situation, it was recommended that the number of candidates accepted to Israeli medical schools be increased and that an additional medical school be opened.

One problem is the shortage of positions for medical students to complete their clinical rotations, which limits the number of students that can be trained each year and contributes to the existing shortage in Israel. Consideration should be given

to an expansion of clinical rotations and the opening of new positions, by, for example, expanding clinical training to two shifts per day, increasing the number of training shifts per year, increasing the number of students per group, and opening clinical rotations outside of the hospitals. The last of these would also help facilitate the migration of hospitalizations and treatments from hospitals to the community.

Recently, the “Ophakim” plan to fully or partially finance Israeli students abroad was implemented, with candidates ranked by their specialty and willingness to work in the periphery. This marks the first time that the country is taking responsibility for Israeli medical students abroad.

Number of medical school graduates in the country per 100,000 population, international comparison

Note: Data are for the most current year available.
 Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Natan Lev, and Baruch Levi,
 Taub Center | Data: OECD

The number of acute care hospital beds in Israel is particularly low

In the graph: In Israel, there were 2 hospital beds per 1,000 population in 2022 including for psychiatric hospitalization, and 1.77 without these — an almost negligible increase over 2021 (1.75 acute care beds per 1,000 population).

Beyond the graph: The absolute number of beds has generally been increasing, however, per capita it has been declining. This reflects the growing global tendency toward transferring care from hospitals to the community. Still, the number of beds in Israel is significantly lower than the OECD average. In 2021, the average number of acute care beds was 1.79 times higher in the OECD.

Apart from the low number of acute care beds, their geographic distribution is also unequal: Tel Aviv and Haifa have the most beds, while the North and South have the fewest. Under the Health Ministry's five-year plan (2023–2028), 1,790 beds will be added — an 11% increase (a total of 17,500 beds). This is a dramatic increase given the relatively small number of beds added since 2010 and the budgetary challenges expected following the war. It is important to track developments in order to discern whether this increase actually materializes.

Number of acute care hospital beds per 1,000 population, international comparison, 2021

Note: Not including psychiatric hospitalization beds.

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Natan Lev, and Baruch Levi, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Prescriptions for opioids has fallen drastically since the health funds changed prescription procedures

Background: After a substantial rise in opioid use in Israel, as reported in a Taub Center study, the Ministry of Health and the health funds began to implement some of the recommendations arising from the Ministry's task force and from meetings with the health funds.

In the graph: The graph shows a sharp drop in first prescriptions for fentanyl, the most powerful opioid, among patients of Clalit Health Services (except for cancer patients) after adding a requirement to receive the authorization of an expert before beginning treatment with fentanyl.

Beyond the graph: In addition, there was an overall drop in fentanyl prescriptions. More research is required to uncover whether patients switched to an alternative pain medication or bought drugs illegally, particularly given reports of widespread forgeries of prescriptions and smuggled medicines. Complementary steps are needed, including prevention (in hospitals as well), building a data base that includes all agencies within the health system and outside it, including welfare and enforcement services, and enhancing accessibility to substance abuse treatment.

First fentanyl prescriptions, Clalit Health Services

Note: First fentanyl prescription, 28-day average.

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Taub Center; Oren Miron and Yannai Kranzler | Data: Clalit Health Services

Since COVID-19, the portion of the population vaccinating has fallen

Background: Vaccinations are one of the most impressive achievements in preventive medicine. In the past few years, in particular following the COVID pandemic, there has been a substantial drop in vaccination rates in the population worldwide. This decline has also been felt in Israel.

In the graphs: Vaccination rates for measles, mumps, rubella, and varicella (MMRV) have declined relative to 2019, just prior to the COVID outbreak. Flu vaccinations are also decreasing, and an examination by socioeconomic status shows that those in the highest socioeconomic clusters (8–10) have the highest vaccination levels while those in the lowest clusters (1–3) have the lowest vaccination rates. This situation requires a comprehensive intervention to raise vaccination rates across the entire population, paying special attention to the weaker population groups.

Vaccination rates for measles, mumps, rubella, and varicella (MMRV)

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Taub Center; Efrat Sales and Deena Zimmerman | Data: Ministry of Health, Timna

Flu vaccination rates in the older population, by age groups and socioeconomic cluster, 2021

Source: Nadav Davidovitch, Taub Center; Efrat Sales | Data: Ministry of Health

Education

We address two issues in the coming pages. With respect to education budgets, an often-heard concern is that per-student budgets differ greatly across the different subsystems. We tested this focusing on high schools, and found that while gaps exist, they have been falling over time. In addition, we found that most of the gaps can be attributed to universal objective criteria. The issue, then, is more with the criteria than with how they are applied.

We look also at budgeting in special education, and show that the current system raises serious concern not only for special education, but for the entire education system.

Finally, we consider accommodations that students receive for the Bagrut (matriculation) exam, show how the portion of accommodations has increased sharply, and explain why and where this is happening and its implications.

A decrease in per-student budgetary gaps in high schools

In the graph: Between 2014 and 2022 there was a substantial narrowing of the gaps in per-student budget between high schools in the Hebrew and Arab education systems. The gap in the average per-student expenditure in the Arab State system and the Hebrew State system was halved (from 32% to 16%), and between the Arab State and the Hebrew State-religious system, it narrowed from 39% to 29%. Within the Hebrew system, the data show different trends — until 2019 the gap between State-religious and State schools grew, and since then, it has decreased.

Beyond the graph: A possible reason for the changes is the growing recognition in the Ministry of Education of the need to narrow these gaps, and, in particular, the disparity between the Hebrew and the Arab education systems. These data clearly show that when the Ministry of Education is determined to narrow gaps, it has the ability to do so. As shown on the next page, the majority of differences that remain are due to the budgeting formulas, which are mostly universal throughout the system.

Differences in per-student expenditure in high school relative to Hebrew State education

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Almost all high school student expenditure gaps result from the budgeting rules, based on objective factors

In the graph: The gaps seen on the previous page can be attributed to a variety of factors. The main source is the type of class (regular classes versus special small classes) and the track (academic or technological). The contribution of sector and supervisory authority are quite small and decreased from 14% in 2017 to 9% in 2022. Note the small aggregate influence of the Nurture index and the periphery index on the budget disparity. Nevertheless, not all of the gap can be explained by objective variables. In 2022, about 16% of the variance remained unexplained. There are those who would view this as still being a large and substantial gap.

Beyond the graph: Although most of the gap in per-student expenditure results from objective budgeting criteria, it is important to determine whether these are justified, or perhaps deserve to be reassessed. For instance, it may be worthwhile to increase the periphery differential in high school budgeting so that it properly reflects the differences in the socioeconomic backgrounds of the student population.

Contribution of explanatory variables to per-student budget in high school

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

A large increase in the portion of special education students receiving a costly personal service basket

Background: As will be shown on the next page, special education costs have risen disproportionately. To better understand this increase, note that students with special needs are divided into two main groups: those attending separate frameworks (special education schools or separate classes in regular schools) and those mainstreamed into regular classes in regular schools. The budget per student varies according to the type of disability, level of functioning, educational level, and organizational framework. To illustrate, the budgeting of separate frameworks can range from NIS 42,000 to NIS 113,000 per year per student in separate

frameworks and from NIS 20,000 to NIS 65,000 per student receiving a personal budget (and less for a student receiving only an institutional basket). Thus, understanding the budget requires examining both the changes in the share of each framework within special education and the changes in the breakdown of students by disability within each framework.

In the graph: The large increase in the share of those receiving a personal basket and decrease in those receiving institutional baskets explains most of the increase shown on the next page.

Distribution of students entitled to special education services, by framework type and budget

Source: Shapira Committee, Education from the Perspective of Special Education, 2023

Special education budgets grew more quickly than regular education budgets

In the graph: As stated on the previous page, one of the Ministry of Education budget items that increased most significantly is special education, from NIS 10.9 billion in 2017 to NIS 16 billion in 2022, an increase of 47%. This is in contrast to an increase of 24% in the regular education budget. Its share of the total budget rose from 18.7% to 21.4%. The number of students eligible for special education services rose at a much faster rate than the total number of students, although at a somewhat slower rate than the budgetary increases.

Beyond the graph: Although these numbers imply that the services provided for special education have grown, there seems to be a feeling of dissatisfaction in recent years among parents of special education students.

Implications: The Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Finance are voicing deep concern that the continuation of current trends in the special education system will lead to a situation whereby the budget allocation to special education will appropriate an unreasonable portion of the education budget, which will harm the regular education system.

Regular and special education budgets

NIS billion

Source: Shapira Committee, Education from the Perspective of Special Education, 2023

A large increase in the proportion of school-granted Bagrut accommodations for learning disabilities

Background: Students with learning disabilities (LDs) face challenges in exams. School systems use testing accommodations to level the playing field. These vary by the extent to which the test is modified and who authorizes them. Most level-1 accommodations (e.g., extended time) are granted by the schools based on teacher recommendations. Level-2 and level-3 accommodations are granted by school district committees, and require didactic evaluations.

In the graph: Over the past decade, the percentage of students granted accommodations due to LDs has increased. This has occurred strictly for school-granted accommodations, while district-granted accommodations have fallen.

Implications: Estimates show that no more than 15% of students suffer from LDs, while 34% of Israeli students received accommodations in 2011 and 54% in 2021. This suggests that factors other than the underlying prevalence of LDs are influencing the numbers receiving accommodations, which threatens their objectivity, fairness, and accuracy as a measure of the student's ability or educational attainment.

Bagrut accommodation trends, by accommodation level

Source: Sarit Silverman, Alex Weinreb, and Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Bagrut exam accommodations for students with learning disabilities are contributing to the socioeconomic achievement gap

Background: The trends shown on the previous page raise concerns about potential conflicts of interest of schools, since they can raise average scores by granting more students school-granted accommodations.

In the graphs: The graphs illustrate the relationships between school-granted accommodations and mathematics achievement, categorized by accommodation type and school SES. For district-granted accommodations, higher levels of accommodations were linked with lower performance, predominantly in higher SES schools. In contrast, school-granted accommodations exhibited a positive relationship

with school mathematics achievement with the disparity more pronounced in the highest SES schools, with a difference of 12.6 points, compared to 2.8 points in the lowest SES schools.

Beyond the graphs: Higher rates of school-granted accommodations also account for most of the rise in Bagrut certification rates in recent years. It also magnifies the success gaps between schools in the Bagrut exams, since higher SES schools grant far more accommodations to their students. Re-designing how test accommodations are granted is imperative not only for students with learning disabilities but for the education system at large.

Weighted math Bagrut scores by accommodation quintile, district- or school-granted, and SES, 2018/2019–2019/2020 school years

Source: Sarit Silverman, Alex Weinreb, and Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education, Transparency in Education website; The Movement for Freedom of Information

Spotlight

Class Size

About a decade ago, 19% of classes had over 32 students, and twenty years ago, it was 37%. The improvement was achieved as a result of a decision to gradually reduce class size to under 32 students. Contributing to the reduction in class size were the steep drop in the fertility rate in the Arab sector, which led to an almost complete halt in growth in the number of students per grade in this sector, as well as the massive construction of classrooms. In this Spotlight, we present the current class sizes in the Israeli education system, focusing on regular classes alone (not including special education classes).

Primary school classes are getting smaller

In the graph: The decrease in class size since the turn of the century is clear. In 2023, there were almost no classes in primary education with more than 36 students, and only 3% of the classes had between 32 and 36 students. Today, the vast majority of students are in classes of between 24 and 32 (83% of classes): in the Hebrew State system — 91% of classes; in the State-religious system — 85%; in the Haredi system — 71%; in the Arab system — 76%; and in the Bedouin system — 83%. In the Druze system, there are no classes with more than 28 students.

Distribution of primary school classes (Grades 1–6), by number of students per class

Note: Regular classes only (excluding special education classes).
Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

The size of middle school classes has barely changed in a decade

In the graph: The Achilles heel of the education system with regard to class size is the middle schools. During the past decade, there has been no improvement in class size in middle schools. In 2023, one-third of students were still in classes of more than 32 students — the same as in 2013. Nonetheless, it is important to note that, in 2000, this figure was 71%.

Beyond the graph: The lack of improvement in class size in middle schools is particularly problematic since this involves children in their early and middle teens, who are especially vulnerable and often display issues with concentration and short attention spans. It is important to point out that class sizes for students in these critical ages are the largest in the education system.

Distribution of middle school classes (Grades 7–9), by number of students per class

Note: Regular classes only (excluding special education classes).
Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Large differences in middle school class size by sector

Background: Grades 7–9 are not always classified as middle school. For instance, in the Haredi education system, there are only two education stages: primary (Grades 1–8) and high school (Grades 9–12).

In the graph: In Grades 7–9, the number of students per class varies greatly across education systems. As in primary education, class sizes in Grades 7–9 are the largest in the Hebrew State system, where 59% of classes have over 32 students, in contrast to only 14% in the State-religious system, 14% in the Haredi system, and 15% in the Arab system. In the Bedouin and Druze education systems, there are almost no classes with more than 32 students. Over the last decade, there have been almost no classes with more than 36 students in the Arab, Druze, and Bedouin education systems.

Distribution of classes in middle schools (Grades 7–9), by sector and supervisory authority, 2023

Note: Regular classes only (excluding special education classes).
Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

The size distribution of high school classes has changed little since the start of the century

Background: In primary and middle schools, small classes are usually for students in special education. In high schools the picture is more complicated as small classes are also used to address the needs of low-achieving students who often come from weaker socioeconomic backgrounds. Thus, reducing class size is the main way the Ministry of Education has implemented a policy of affirmative action.

In the graph: The figure shows the situation for the regular education system. The data indicate that between 2000 and 2023, the proportion of large classes out of total regular classes fell only slightly, from 29% in 2000, to 26% in 2023.

Beyond the graph: Looking at the entire education system, the situation has changed only slightly in more than two decades. The share of small classes (up to 24 students) rose from 29% in 2000 to 31% in 2023, while the share of large classes (36 students or more) fell from 5% to 3%.

Distribution of high school classes (Grades 10–12), by number of students per class

Note: Regular classes only (excluding special education classes).

Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

The portion of high school students in small classes has increased in all sectors, but fallen in the last decade in non-Haredi Jewish schools

In the graph: The share of students in small classes (Mabar, Lev, Tov, and other programs where affirmative action is applied) rose during the past twenty years from 8% to 22%. There is a significant difference between the Hebrew and Arab sectors in this regard. In the former, the change in affirmative action policy occurred primarily between 2000 and 2012, so the portion of students in small classes grew only until 2012 and since then fell. In the Arab sector affirmative action was implemented throughout the period (2000–2023), so the percentage continued growing. Affirmative action is applied on a particularly large scale in the Bedouin sector.

Portion of students (Grades 10–12) in small classes, by sector and supervisory authority

Note: Small classes are programs such as Mabar, Lev, and Tov.
Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Early Childhood

In this section, we will explore several issues concerning early childhood. We start with a survey conducted by the Center regarding emotional and behavioral difficulties exhibited by young children as a result of the war, covering issues such as changes in sleeping patterns, attachment behavior, and displays of anger. We continue with a variety of issues including the effect of a death in the family on a child's later success and difficulties in daycare staffing.

Parents report regressive behaviors in their children following the outbreak of the war

Background: In a Taub Center survey conducted in January 2024, some 1,200 parents to young children were asked to compare their child's pre-war and post-war behavior focusing on regressive behaviors since the start of the war, which can signify emotional difficulties among young children.

In the graph: About a third of parents reported that their young children exhibited more or much more emotional difficulties following the war. For instance, 43% of parents reported their children are more easily startled by sudden noises, 36% reported that their children have more separation anxiety, and 34% reported that their children have more difficulties sleeping since the start of the war. With this, most parents report no change in their children's behavior.

Beyond the graph: The analysis shows a direct and statistically significant correlation between the child's level of difficulties and regressive behavior relative to the period before the war as reported by the parents, and the self-reported emotional state of the parents. That is, as levels of reported parental depression, fear, and stress rise, so do their children experience greater reported difficulties.

Changes in the behavior of young children since the beginning of the war

Note: Based on parental reports.
Source: Blank et al., Taub Center

The loss of a parent or a sibling at a young age harms future academic achievements similarly

Background: There is a negative relation between a death of a member of the nuclear family when a child is young and their likelihood of qualifying for a Bagrut later in life. This relation is retained even when controlling for background demographic and socioeconomic variables related to both the probability of being exposed to such an event and academic achievements.

In the graph: The chances of a child who has experienced the loss of a parent or a sibling to qualify for a Bagrut certificate is only 74% of that of someone who has not. There is no significant difference between the loss of a parent and that of a sibling. This finding is surprising given the central role of a parent, particularly in the first few years of a child's life.

Beyond the graph: This finding demonstrates the benefits of lending assistance in cases of civilian death. Institutional assistance, currently unavailable for bereaved siblings, could help lower gaps that could result from the death of a brother or sister in early childhood.

The relative likelihood of qualifying for a Bagrut among someone who has experienced a death in the nuclear family when they were young relative to someone who has not experienced such a death

Source: Navon et al., Taub Center | Data: CBS

Early childhood population growth rates for Haredim and Arabs projected to fall

In the graph: The projected early childhood annual growth rate in Israel is expected to remain about 1.4% through 2032, with considerable variability across subpopulations. Currently, annual growth rates among Haredim and Arabs are greater than among non-Haredi Jews and Others. However, these are expected to decline over the next decade. Among non-Haredi Jews and Others, the annual growth rate may outpace the Arab annual growth rate by 2030.

Beyond the graph: The portion of non-Haredi Jewish and Other children in the population of young children in Israel is currently the majority of children from birth to age 6, but it is likely to dip below 50% by the end of the decade.

Implications: This ongoing change has ramifications for the education system and for social and economic policy, which will need to adapt to shifts in educational streams, and adjust budgetary needs to ensure an adequate supply of teachers. Also, since poverty rates among young children are highest among Arab and Haredi families, a rise in their proportion will likely require increased support and services for families in poverty.

Projected early childhood (birth to age 6) annual growth rates, by sector

Source: Sarit Silverman and Carmel Blank, Taub Center | Data: CBS

A serious shortage of staff in daycare centers

Background: In May 2023, the government presented a 5-year plan with goals to lower childcare costs to parents, expand the daycare system, and improve the quality of care through training for the caregivers and staff guidance (the two last steps were cancelled in 2024 because of budget cuts).

In the graph: In a Taub Center survey among more than 1,000 daycare workers and managers, over 80% of subsidized and two-thirds of private daycare center managers reported that they are understaffed at least one or two days a week. Many respondents reported that they operate with missing staff three days a week or more.

Beyond the graph: Over 90% of responding daycare center managers reported difficulties recruiting new staff, while almost 60% of caregivers in subsidized daycare centers and 40% of caregivers in private daycare centers reported that they often considered quitting.

Note: The survey sample is not representative, so the conclusions may not be indicative of a population-wide phenomenon. Still, the responses raise serious concerns.

Under-staffing in Israeli daycare centers

Source: Sarit Silverman and Carmel Blank, Taub Center | Data: Carmel Blank, Taub Center

Environment & Health

At different points in time, Israel agreed to comply with various goals in the area of the environment. For instance, in signing the Paris Climate Accords (2015), the government agreed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 30% by 2030, and in 2021, Israel committed to increase renewable energy from about 10% of current production to 20% by 2030. In this section, we present some areas where the state has not succeeded in attaining the goals it committed to or has not taken sufficient steps to deal with climate change in order to reduce the health implications that accompany it.

Production of electricity from renewable energy sources is lower in the winter months

Background: Reducing carbon dioxide emissions requires mainly the production of energy from renewable sources, which can be partially facilitated by a move to electric vehicles. Using renewable energies to produce electricity began in Israel in 2012, and has risen over time — from 0.3% of total production in 2012 to 10% in 2022. The national goals are 20% by 2025 and 30% by 2030 of production, however, an updated forecast shows that we will reach only 14% by 2025 and 19% by 2030. Importantly, Israel's goals are among the lowest in OECD countries.

In the graph: The ability to produce electricity from renewable sources fluctuates over the course of the year due to seasonal variation. As shown in the graph, the share of electricity produced from renewable sources is higher in the spring months than in winter or summer months. This trend has been stable over the years. Solar energy is responsible for over 90% of the electricity produced from renewable sources.

Beyond the graph: In the spring months, the angle of the sun relative to the earth is optimal for producing solar energy. In addition, skies are clear and cloud and sand-storm free, days lengthen, and temperatures are mild. All of these factors contribute to the efficiency of solar panels in the spring. It is important to remember that, in Israel, energy consumption in the summer is higher than in the spring due to the widespread use of air conditioning, so that the share of solar energy out of total energy consumption decreases.

It is possible to increase renewable energy production by giving incentives to build energy storage facilities and for the development of transmission networks that are able to absorb the electricity produced from renewable sources.

Proportion of production of electricity from renewable sources out of total production, by month

Source: Maya Sadeh and Rakefet Shafran-Nathan, Taub Center | Data: Noga

Climate change has led to a considerable increase in the heat burden over the past decades

Background: Observations conducted since the 1950s in different regions of the world indicate a consistent rise in both the strength and duration of heat waves. According to projections of the US Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, this trend is expected to continue even more forcefully in the coming decades. In Israel, the average temperature has risen since the 1940s by about 1.6 degrees Celsius. Temperature rises and exposure to heat burden influence health in a variety of ways, both direct and indirect, beginning with impacting pre-existing health conditions and increasing the risk of death by harming the ability to spend time outside or to engage in physical activities outside.

In the graph: In Israel, a 40% increase in the number of meteorological stations that have measured a heat burden categorized as *extreme caution* by the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) has been noted.

This means a danger of seizures and heat stroke during outdoor activities. In addition, the number of stations that measured a heat burden of *immediate danger* (risk of heat stroke during periods spent outdoors) rose from 1% in the 1950s to 4% in the last decade.

Beyond the graph: As a rule, the level of risk from heat burden is higher in urban areas due to the creation of urban heat islands. The major cause of these are a lack of ventilation, building and road paving materials, and the ratio of building cover to vegetation. These factors can be changed to improve our abilities to adapt to climate change. With this, the risk level is also dependent on other factors related to the building quality, including things like weatherproofing of buildings, access to electricity and air-conditioning, and the ability of the population to afford electricity costs.

Average exposure to heat stress at 2:00 PM in the summer months (May 15–September 15), by decade

Note: The percentages in each pie slice are the share of meteorological stations in the relevant category for the decade according to the NOAA index.

Source: Maya Sadeh and Rakefet Shafran-Nathan, Taub Center | Data: Israel Meteorological Service

Tree shade in large cities is low, especially in those areas where it is most needed

Background: As a result of the rise in heat burden described on the previous page, in January 2022, the government set an ambitious goal of creating tree shading in about 70% of city streets by 2040 in order to reduce the heat burden in urban spaces and to prevent the creation of urban heat islands, which can be hotter by 1–5 degrees Celsius than the environs. Green spaces, and particularly trees, have an important influence on health and feelings of thermal comfort and quality of urban life. It also leads to a decrease in energy demands for cooling and the emission of greenhouse gases.

In the graph: In the largest cities (Tel Aviv, Jerusalem, and Haifa) the rate of shading increases as socioeconomic status rises. In Rehovot, Netanya, and Be'er Sheva no such relationship is seen.

Beyond the graph: The World Health Organization has determined that the most vulnerable populations to climate change, and, in particular, to increased heat burden, are those of low socioeconomic status. It is particularly important to enhance the areas where these populations are concentrated.

Average proportion of shading from trees in selected cities, by socioeconomic cluster, 2020

Source: Maya Sadeh and Rakefet Shafran-Nathan, Taub Center | Data: CBS; Survey of Israel

The amount of greenhouse gas emissions does not show signs of decreasing

In the graph: According to the national emissions report of the Ministry of Environmental Protection, carbon dioxide emissions were 79% of all emissions in 2022 and methane emissions were 14%. The remaining emissions were primarily refrigerant gases (HFCs). The emission levels in 2022 were higher than at the start of the century but the same as in 2015. This follows a slight decline between 2015 and 2021 and a rise of 3.4% in 2022 (when the rate of increase in electricity production from traditional sources was greater than the rate of increase of production from renewable sources). The relative shares of gas emissions has barely changed over this period.

Beyond the graph: Carbon dioxide emissions result from the burning of fossil fuels (coal, mazut, diesel, emissions from quarrying, and more). Methane is produced primarily by gas emissions from landfill (63%), raising animals (27%), and waste management (9.7%). A look at emissions in 2022 relative to 2021 shows that the amount of emissions of carbon dioxide rose by about 3.5%, methane production by about 3%, and the amount of emissions from refrigerants grew by about 7%.

Greenhouse gas emissions by source

Thousands of tons

Source: Maya Sadeh and Rakefet Shafran-Nathan, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Environmental Protection

The share of domestic waste burial is among the highest in high-income countries

In the graph: In contrast to the OECD countries, where the recycling rates are on average 60% (40% landfill), in 2021, the recycling rate in Israel was only about 20% — among the lowest in the OECD. This rate has risen by only a few percentage points since 2013. In light of this, the Ministry of Environmental Protection’s vision of sustainable waste management and the move from a linear to a circular economy by 2050, as in Belgium and the Netherlands, seems far from attainable.

Beyond the graph: Burying waste is accompanied by a variety of negative environmental effects, among them greenhouse gas emissions (primarily methane), air pollution, contamination of groundwater and soil, and harm to open areas. According to the State Comptroller’s Report, in 2022, five landfill sites were due to be closed, and within a year to three years there will no longer be approved sites for waste burial. The implication of these deficiencies in waste treatment could lead to a dire sanitation crisis in Israel, in addition to the negative environmental effects from the waste burial.

Domestic waste burial rates, Israel and selected OECD countries

Note: For Italy, Portugal and Türkiye the latest available data are from 2020.
 Source: Maya Sadeh and Rakefet Shafran-Nathan, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Demography

Israel's demography is changing, with decreases in fertility in all parts of society and an increase in migration, especially of those defined as *Other* (not Jewish or Arab). Life expectancy has begun to rise once again after the decline due to COVID and the death rate has decreased. With that, there has been a sharp increase in violent deaths in Israel, especially among Arabs.

A drop in fertility rates across all population groups

Background: Fertility rates started falling in Israel in 2018. Despite a minor COVID-related fertility boost in 2021, trends returned to their pre-COVID downward trajectory in 2022. This reduction in fertility can be seen among Jews, Arabs, and Others.

In the graph: Official CBS data on trends in the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) show reductions across all religious groups, though the two largest religious groups, Jews and Muslims, maintain high fertility by international standards. By 2022, the TFR of Jewish and Muslim women had fallen to 3.03 and 2.91, respectively. Each of these is far above replacement-level fertility, which is approximately 2.08 in Israel.

Among all smaller religious groups, fertility is already much lower, and it fell further. By 2022, the TFR of Christian and Druze women had reached 1.68 and 1.85, respectively. Among those categorized as having no religion, TFR reached 1.26 by 2022. This is deep into lowest-low fertility levels that have characterized much of southern and eastern Europe since the 1990s.

Total Fertility Rate (TFR) in Israel, by religion

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

On-going reductions in fertility

In the graph: The observed declines in fertility up to 2022 intensified over 2023. Among Jewish and Arab women, the monthly trend in the General Fertility Rate (GFR) — the monthly number of births per 1,000 women aged 15–49 — was, respectively, 3.0% and 1.7% lower in 2023 than in 2022, which points to a continued downward trend in fertility that, as shown on the previous page, began in 2018. This downward trend appears to have continued into the first two months of 2024, especially in the Arab population.

The General Fertility Rate (GFR), by month, for Jewish and Arab women, 2019–2023

Note: The GFR is the number of births per 1,000 women aged 15–49. Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Until October 2023, Israel's death rate was lower than in any prior year

Background: Between 2019, the last pre-COVID year, and 2023, the population aged 70+ grew by 19%, whereas the general population grew by 7.6%. The increasing share that is elderly is supposed to drive up the Crude Death Rate (CDR) since the probability of death increases sharply with age.

In the graph: Based on the monthly number of deaths until the October 7 war, 2023 was the first year in Israel's history in which the CDR was expected to drop below 5 deaths per 1,000 individuals. The sudden spike in deaths associated with October 7th and the subsequent war can be seen in the figure. These pushed overall deaths back towards 50,000, raising the actual CDR to 5.1. The number of deaths in the first quarter of 2024 was also higher than in 2023.

Beyond the graph: The reduction in the CDR until October occurred despite the rapid growth of Israel's elderly population. This is noteworthy and it suggests that were it not for the war, Israel's life expectancy would be heading back toward its pre-COVID upward trajectory.

Number of deaths by month, 2021–2023, and crude death rate, 1997–2023

a. Monthly number of deaths

b. Crude death rate

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

The share of births from IVF is increasing as women's mean age at first birth rises

Background: Globally, ongoing rises in women's education, economic autonomy, and shifting aspirations regarding work and family are leading to an increase in mean age at first birth. In most countries, this is associated with a reduction in fertility, in part because fecundability also falls as women head into their 30s. One of the solutions to this has been to use Assisted Reproductive Technology (ART), mostly In Vitro Fertilization (IVF). Israel has the most generous public provision of ART of any country. It provides full funding for treatment cycles up to two children through 26 IVF centers. Still, more than 60% of the cycles are performed in the private healthcare sector.

In the graph: The rise in age at first birth in Israel is strongly associated with a rise in the share of births conceived with ART. Between 2005 and 2019, the number of IVF births rose from 4,772 births, accounting for 3.3% of all live births, to 9,176 births, accounting for 5.0% of all live births.

Age at first birth and share of births associated with IVF treatment

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

The main driver of population growth across religious groups is very different

In the graph: Israel's overall population growth rate in 2023 was 1.86%. The graph shows the overall growth rates for each of Israel's five major religious groups between 2015 and 2022, while disaggregating those rates into its two sources — from fertility and migration. The height of each column indexes its annual growth rate in percentage terms.

Among Jews, Muslims, and Druze, growth rates remain high relative to other high-income countries, but have been trending down. In all of these groups, growth is largely driven by fertility (wholly in the case of the Druze).

Both in terms of magnitude and sources of demographic growth, Israel's Other population has quite different patterns. From 2015 to 2019, its annual rate of increase rose from 3.9% to 5.7%, making it the fastest growing subpopulation in Israel. In 2022, the Other population grew 11.2%, with 97% of this growth driven by net migration due, mostly, to the Russia-Ukraine war, and in 2023 by 6.2%.

Beyond the graph: Israel's population is slated to pass the 10 million mark in 2024. Without the contribution of the Others, who now outnumber the combined Druze and Christian population by about 60%, that would not have happened until around 2027.

Annual population growth rates, by religious group and source of growth

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Small distortions in sex ratios at birth in Israel's Arab population

Background: The sex ratio at birth (SRB) falls in a very small range across all societies: for every 100 girls born, there are between 102.7–106.7 boys. In many Asian societies that experienced sharp reductions in fertility since the 1980s this ratio rose, mostly because parents used sex-selective abortion or, more recently, sex-selective implantation, to give birth to boys. A rule of thumb is that any SRB above 107 is evidence of such intervention.

In the graph: There are mild distortions in the SRB in minority religious groups in Israel across the 2002–2022 period. As expected, given the timing of their fertility reductions, we initially see it in the Druze and Christian Arab population, combined here since they are small populations. From around 2017, just before the rapid reduction in Muslim fertility began, we also see an increase in the Muslim SRB to around 107 in the 2019–2021 period.

Implications: These are mild distortions. However, they will magnify existing gender imbalance in Israeli Arab society, and the accompanying problems.

Sex ratio at birth in Israel, by religion

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Homicides in Israel's Arab population tripled between 2019 and 2023

In the graph: The homicide rate has been climbing rapidly in Israel's Arab population since 2018. After a mild but promising reduction in 2022, the number of homicides more than doubled in 2023. Of the 299 homicides in 2023, 78% were within the Arab sector despite comprising only 21% of

the population. There was also a shift in seasonal patterns, with no reductions during the January–March period. In fact, the only substantial reduction was in October 2023, in the immediate aftermath of the Hamas attacks and the beginning of the Gaza War.

Monthly number of homicides, 2016–2023, by subpopulation

Source: Weinreb et al., Taub Center | Data: Israel Police

Increasing inequality between Jews and Arabs in the risk of death from homicide

In the graph: The dark blue line is the ratio of the Arab to Jewish crude homicide rate (number of murders per 1,000 people). The light blue line is the ratio of the rate weighted by the number of younger males (number of murders per 1,000 men aged 20–34). These ratios averaged around 4:1 on both rates until around 2015, and were around 10:1 and 8:1 on the crude rate and younger men rate, respectively, in the 2020–2022 period. In 2023, these ratios climbed to 13:1 and 10:1, respectively.

Beyond the graph: The ratio of Arab to Jewish homicide rates is about 60% greater than the ratio of Black to White homicide rates in the US, which is around 8:1.

Ratio of Arab:Jewish homicide rates

Source: Weinreb et al., Taub Center | Data: CBS; Israel Police

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